

SHORT NOTES

PREPARATION OF THE FORMATES OF RARE EARTH ELEMENTS

BY BALARAM SAHOO, S. PANDA AND D. PATNAIK

A convenient method for the preparation of formates of the rare earth elements is not available in the literature. The method adopted by us involves the reaction of the nitrates of the desired elements with formic acid. The formates are easily obtained by this method, and these contain 0.25 molecules of water of hydration.

The nitrates of lanthanum and cerium used were of E. Merck 'extrapure' quality and that of thorium used was of B.D.H. Analar quality. Formic acid of E. Merck 'extrapure' quality was used. Since the reaction of nitrates of these elements with formic acid was vigorous, the nitrates were added in small quantities at a time to 20 c.c. of formic acid taken in a flask. When evolution of gases involving nitrous fumes had ceased, a considerable quantity of salt was formed. The formates settled down in granular form. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and the precipitate was again refluxed for 2 hours with a fresh quantity of formic acid. The precipitates were filtered off and kept in a vacuum desiccator over solid caustic soda. In case of the thorium formate, heating the precipitate at 80-90° under vacuum was carried out. The compounds have been tested to be free from nitrogen.

The oxide content after ignition was determined as described previously (Patnaik and Panda, *Curr. Sci.*, 1956, 25, 287). For the estimation of the formate content the method adopted was first to dissolve a weighed quantity of the salt in a fixed volume of $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Then $N/10\text{-NaOH}$ solution was added in slight excess of the volume required for bringing about complete hydrolysis. After heating to boiling, the hydroxide of the rare earth was filtered off. The solution was next acidified with H_2SO_4 and again made alkaline with solid Na_2CO_3 after which the estimation was carried out according to the standard method.

It is not possible to determine directly the associated water by the method of Brush and Penfield as the compounds undergo decomposition on heating. Attempt was made to determine the water content by the method of isothermal dehydration. It was found that up to 90° water could not be completely removed and when the dehydration was carried above 90°, decomposition of the compound started. Therefore semimicro combustion method was adopted for the estimation of total hydrogen and carbon. This would give an extra amount of 1.5 mole of water for each mole of lanthanum and cerous formates and 2 moles of water per mole of thorium formate, resulting from the decomposition of the formate groups, in addition to the associated water. The experimental results along with the calculated values of the formates, assuming to be associated with 0.25 molecules of water, agree quite satisfactorily within the limits of experimental error.

The presence of a small fractional number of water molecules in such heavy metal formates makes it beyond the scope of experiment to rigidly decide that the number of hydration should be 0.25. Without any detriment to the permissible percentage of error of the various experimental data, the number of water of crystallisation may lie within the range 0.25 to 0.30. Of all the analyses for the constituents of the hydrated formate, the determination of metallic oxide is the most accurate one, and so in consideration of this fact, we are in favour of 0.25 molecules of water to be associated with each molecule of the rare earth formate.